

The Cherubim and Seraphim Church of Zion, Ugbonla

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Entry tags: Religious Group, The Cherubim and Seraphim Church of Zion, Ugbonla, Aladura

The Cherubim and Seraphim Church of Zion was founded on 16th February 1948 in Ugbonla, Ilaje area on the eastern flank of Yorubaland in southwest Nigeria. It is an offshoot of the Cherubim and Seraphim (C & S) Society, a Christian movement which started as a praying group comprising crowds (people) who thronged the home where Abiodun Akinsowon was resident after she had a mysterious encounter. Abiodun had peeped into the chalice of a religious procession and had gone into a trance for days until Moses Tunolase Orimolade was contacted to help restore her to life. This occurred in 1925 in Lagos, Nigeria. As the society began to meet to pray and fellowship, two brothers of Ilaje origin who had visited Lagos and joined the C & S Society and had become very active members of the group. The two brothers (Alfred and Timothy Orogbemi) returned to Ilajeland in 1929 and introduced the C & S Society to their homeland. The society grew steadily till it began experiencing some internal crisis at about 1942. Some of her members had accused the church of its acquiescence with the local authority regarding the practice of twin infanticide sanctioned by the latter at the time. The aggrieved members began to pull out of the society as early as 1945 and had predicted that the church will lose its relevance in Ilajeland if it fails to rise to condemn the practice they considered unacceptable. It is widely believed among the antagonists of the practice that had the founder of the C & S Zion Church failed to pull out of the larger society in their homeland and established a reformed version of the church, the C & S Society in Ilajeland, the church would have lost currency with the people. While the Holy Apostles community, Ayetoro (the first successful theocratic community in Ilajeland) took on a unique description of the interconnectivity between faith and woks and thus had a successful economic and technological campaign, the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla founded one year after Ayetoro had a spiritual expansionist outlook. The latter expanded its influence and dominance in the area by successfully galvanising the almost fifty other smaller theocratic settlements which sprang up after it. Saint Elisha Lene Ogunfeyimi, the founder of Ugbonla community laid the foundation for several of the doctrinal guidelines which most of the other theocratic communities in Ilajeland subsequently adopted. Ugbonla boasts of hundreds of branches across three continents of the world. The church has branches in most of the coastal states in Nigeria, Cameroon, Gabon and in the United States and Great Britain.

Date Range: 1948 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ugbonla Community in Ilajeland

Region tags: Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Ilajeland, Ugbonla

Ugbonla, a theocratic community and the headquarters of the Cherubim and Seraphim Church of Zion is located to the east of Ode-Ugbo the seat of the revered traditional stool of the Ugbo clan in Ilajeland. Due to the proximity of Ilajeland to the Atlantic Ocean, the region is for a larger part of the year waterlogged. Intra and inter community movement around and among the nearly 180 communities in the area is by canoes and recently, speedboats. The Ilaje area is home to about fifty

theocratic communities of which Ugbonla is one of the four most prominent.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 2: Omoyajowo, J. Akinyele, *Cherubim and Seraphim: The History of an African Independent Church* (New York: NOK, 1982)
- Source 3: Omogbemi, C.O, *Leneism: Key to Zion Renaissance* (Lagos: Inspiration Communications, 2008)
- Source 1: Religious Expressions, Theocratic Communities and Cultural Identity in the Ilaje Coastline of Southwest Nigeria since 1930.

Notes: No substantial work has been done on the Cherubim and Seraphim Church of Zion, Ugbonla. Only passing references have been made to the group in works on the Aladura Movement in Nigeria. In some cases, these references are as brief as few sentences or just a paragraph in the few books available. The source referenced above is the PhD thesis of this author which focussed on four of the most prominent theocratic settlements in Ilajeland. Ugbonla happens to be one of the four theocratic settlements studied in the work. The thesis was written in the department of Religious Studies and submitted to the Postgraduate College of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. It was completed in late 2020.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/search/top?q=cherubim%20and%20seraphim%20church%20of%20zion%20ugbonla>
- Source 1 Description: Saint Elisha Lene and members of the C & S church of Zion in a procession during the church anniversary
- Source 2 URL: https://www.facebook.com/watch?ref=search&v=1061606564351343&external_log_id=4ab4c899-ce44-440c-9954-11ee1c0b2616&q=cherubim%20and%20seraphim%20church%20of%20zion%20ugbonla%20headquarters%2C..
- Source 2 Description: members of the Ugbonla community in a religious festival

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.africanportal.net/ABO/BibeliAtoka/>
- Source 1 Description: YORUBA REFERENCE BIBLE ONLINE: BIBELI YORUBA ATŌKA

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: The Cherubim and Seraphim Church of Zion, Ugbonla is a dominant Christian group in Ilajeland southwest Nigeria. It originated from the Cherubim and Seraphim movement which started in 1925. It however adopted some reforms which made it relevant to meet the immediate needs of the population in its locality. Though the church interacts with other Christian movements of its kind in Ilajeland, it is distinct in identity and firm in its beliefs and doctrines such that its values are not easily eroded by any Christian movement it interacts with locally and globally.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The church honours invitations to participate in religious programmes organised by sister churches in its area. It also extends invitations to Christian communities which it considers friendly and judges as professing faith similar to theirs. It is however never in a hurry to imbibe or embrace practices which are found among neighbouring Christian communities. As such, it would be appropriate describe the Cherubim and Seraphim (C & S) Zion Church as one which maintains cultural contact only with Christian communities around it. It dissociates itself completely from those who subscribe to the autochthonous traditional religious beliefs around them.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The church is not neutral nor amorphous in terms of its cultural contact. The church holds a view about the superiority of their faith tradition and are exceedingly proud of their theological and exegetical positions. They are quick to draw the line when they come in contact with religious practices which they consider to be at variance with theirs. They proceed to reiterate their convictions and challenge their members to follow the precepts and ordinances of the church always.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Apart from the period immediately before and after the founding of the first and second theocratic communities in Ilajeland (1945 - 1947) when members of the group were drawn in a fierce battle with the traditional authority in Ilajeland, there has been no violent conflicts between this community and others around them. However, there are insinuations and rumours of mild doses of healthy and not-too-healthy competitions between Ugbonla and some other theocratic communities around them in the past.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: No records of violent conflicts exists between the C & S Zion Church Ugbonla and groups outside the sample region

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Children born by members of the group are ascribed some degree of membership. They are free to participate in church programmes and belong to age appropriate groups until they are promoted by the church leadership or in some cases decide on the group they intend to function in as adult members.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: This applies to adults who voluntarily decide on joining the group. This was the most prevalent method of membership subscription in the early days of the community. Majority of the members in recent times were either born by parents who belonged to the group or have been familiar with them in some other ways. The church has grown and spread across their immediate region as well as to distant territories.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There are no class considerations in the church membership subscription.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There is no strict age at which membership of the church is ascribed or conferred on intending members. Although members willing to undergo the biennial theological training of the church must be of the age of accountability which generally is conceived as a mature teenager or full adult. This formal training culminates in an ordination service for graduands who are then conferred with official titles and recognised as full members of the church.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Membership of the church is open to interested member of the public who identify either as male or female

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: This is the official mode of assigning group membership in the C & S Church of Zion. Full membership of the church is assigned at the completion of the biennial theological training of the church which runs for a period of six months. During the training, trainees are led through a series of lectures ranging from the church doctrines, study of significant bible characters, leadership programme and other topical issues in church administration among other things.

Graduands are usually presented for ordination and conferment of clerical titles at a ceremony after their baptism at the end of the year.

Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Notes: There are no other factors known which qualifies prospects for membership

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Though the church holds special programmes which include spiritual awakening conferences, most of their programmes are held in the community or church branches and are targeted mostly towards their members. Ugbonla is a community founded mainly for religious purposes. It was established to allow members of the group uninterrupted freedom to practice their faith and be separate from encumbrances which would make bring impediments to their aim of a life of worship. Because the church has become very popular especially in Ilajeland, members in branches of the church and at times locals in and around Ilajeland visit the community during their special programmes but return to their homes at the completion of the convocations. Either during such special programmes or at other times, anyone willing to join the church is usually allowed to do so.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: When the founder of the faith was still alive, he commanded considerable respect and following largely in their local environment but was equally patronised by notable politicians in the country. Sometimes, he was influential enough use his popularity to the advantage of political actors of his preference. Those who knew him well to appreciate his popularity sought his blessings and support for their political ambitions. Neither he nor his group however had official political support of the national government though his contributions to the political climate of his environment was recognised.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The church has been consistent with their belief and has continued to hold fast to their faith. As it often happens in the life cycle of organizations of this nature, there is a record of some spiritual lull in this generation of their membership compared to what is known of the previous generation.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 6365

Notes: Ugbonla as the headquarters of the C & S Church of Zion worldwide has a population of permanent residents in excess of 1000 adults. However, when members of the church living outside of this town and who worship regularly in church branches in their various locations are reckoned, the number would rise significantly to more than 50000. Nigeria's national population census conducted in 1991 puts the figure of Ugbonla's population at 6,365. However, the number of permanent adult

residents in the town has declined to just above 1000. This is due to two significant reasons; one, the crisis which rocked the church upon the demise of the founder and first leader of the group, Saint Elisha Lene Ogunfeyimi in 1996 had split the church into splinter groups. Some former members have sided with those who lost out in the succession tussle. Secondly, the Ilaje and their Ijaw neighbours were involved in an intertribal war between 1997 and 1998 which left Ugbonla invaded and plundered. Most residents fled the town after which homes were looted and set ablaze. Some buildings are yet to be rebuilt till date. Aside these numbers, several hundreds others have become less active and so may not be regarded as active members anymore.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 12.68

Notes: Nigeria's National Population commission put Ugbonla's population at 6365 in 1991 while the Ilaje region where Ugbonla is located was said to have 50188 inhabitants from the census report. This leave Ugbonla with 12.68% of Ilaje's total population as at 1991. There has been only one other census conducted in 2006. However, its figures were disputed across a section of the nation.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: The C & S Church of Zion, Ugbonla was one of the earliest groups in the C & S fold in Ilajeland to modify its operational methodology. The founder of the group led his followers to the uninhabited jungle formerly dreaded for being the dumpsite of corpses of those who died under mysterious circumstances and those of lunatics. His decision to inhabit the land was seen as outrageous by a section of the local population. He however transformed the space to a sacred arena in Ilajeland. During the life time of its founder, Saint Elisha Lene Ogunfeyimi and at the peak of the church's popularity, the ministry was accorded the leadership position among almost fifty other smaller theocratic communities of the C & S stock patterned after his innovative style in Ilajeland. The church still maintains its dominance in the region though its control of the numerous other theocratic settlements has waned.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Ugbonla is a theocratic community. In this sense, the political and religious leadership of the community are fused together and held by one individual addressed as Oba (king). The current Oba is the second and a direct son of the founder. He is supported by a group of prophets with whom he administers the community. There are other levels of leadership which include elders and other gifted spiritual leaders.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The leadership of the C & S Church of Zion Ugbonla superintends over all branches of the church within and outside Nigeria. The Oba or kabiyesi provides leadership from the headquarters of the ministry. He disseminates vital information through the conference chairmen to local church leadership. A conference is a number of local churches in an area which are grouped together for the spiritual edification of the members. Conference chairmen are ranking prophets or leaders of a local church within the jurisdiction of the conference they lead. A conference may be loosely described as an equivalent of a diocese with some operational distinctiveness from the way they are conceived in the orthodox or mainline churches. At times the Oba may reach the local church leadership directly without going through the conference chairmen. However, after the birth of the Ugbonla experiment, there are numerous C & S churches which have sprang up in Ilajeland and in other locations. These churches have their own distinct leadership and operate independent of Ugbonla

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Notes: Though the conference chairman exercises some control over his contemporaries who serve as overseers of single congregations within the conference, they lack the kind of authority ascribed to bishops in the orthodox churches. Local leaders in certain cases object to the control of conference leaders and even refuse to recognise their authority. They sometimes bring such cases to the notice of the Oba who tries to resolve the dispute and encourages them to work together.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: There exist conference chairmen who oversee the activities within their jurisdiction. However, they do not exercise absolute powers.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The council that exists in each conference is comprised of leaders of each local assembly within the conference. They meet to plan on important activities within the conference and sometimes deliberate on plans to assist a local assembly in prosecuting major activities or programmes. It is only an advisory council which has limited powers over the local assemblies which constitute the conference. In some cases, the conference leadership and its chairman may be positioned to exercise different degrees of control over individual local assemblies within their jurisdiction. For example, a newly established assembly with a younger cleric may be more receptive of advice and guidance from the conference chairman and its leadership than an assembly with a more experienced or vocal leader.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

Notes: This is not very easy to determine. However, in each local assembly, there exists the members at the basic level. The next level is that of ordained worker who have undergone the church theological training. Another level which though may be a bit unofficial is that of the activity group (unit) leaders. They support the key leaders, elders and prophets who are in turn answerable to the leader of the local assembly. This hierarchy is almost the same in the local assembly as with the headquarter church. The Oba is the overall leader and highest authority in the headquarter (Ugbonla). He receives reports, complaints and is kept abreast of important activities and happenings in the local assembly.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders are believed to possess supernatural powers and qualities in the C & S church of Zion. The late founder and numerous prophets who worked with him were reputed to have possessed uncommon powers to heal the sick, bring good fortunes as well as avert misfortunes and perform other miraculous feats. They were widely acclaimed to have used their uncommon spiritual powers to establish, grow and develop their community which was once a dreadful place in Ilajeland. The current leaders of local assemblies and especially the Oba are equally ascribed supernatural powers. They are believed upon by their members as being capable of intervening in their lives and with the power of their prayers attract supernatural solutions to their challenges

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: The C & S church of Zion does not hold this belief

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that the closer an individual is to God, the better positioned the individual is to lead an extra-ordinary life which includes being exceptionally useful in their religious circle. The church and her members place significant importance on the religious dimension of their being and so hold that individual deeds carried out by their members in the current life which synchronise with their idea of what matters most to them in life counts for the unleashing of greater powers to them for greater usefulness. They conceive of the enormous spiritual powers of their leaders as the direct consequence of their devotion, dedication and consecration to their God

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: They hold that power is imparted either through the medium of their leaders or directly from God himself. They generally conceive of power as a force that is released to those who are diligent to seek it or to whom it is freely given.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that their founder and other founding leaders were impacted with power from God. This belief is still widely held by them till date. Every leader or individual who possesses and exercises the use of some spiritual powers is regarded as having obtained the power to the pleasure of God, the supernatural being.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: Even if it happens that an individual receives some spiritual powers after an encounter with a leader, such power is still held as having been sourced from God. In such situation, the leader has only been used to impart the power as a vessel of transmission.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: This is true in the case of prophets. Prophets are conceived as the most powerful and significant category of leaders among the C & S church of Zion. In this regard, powers are associated with this leadership office. They are held as being able to gain access into secret events and transmit them to those who may need to profit from the knowledge of such occurrences or events. They are conceived of as a nightmare to evil doers and a source of support to good people. Other categories of leaders may operate under mysterious circumstances occasionally. At such times, they are looked upon with the same awe and admiration prophets are accorded in the normal discharge of their spiritual assignment

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders across the C & S church of Zion usually emerge through a selection process. The path adopted in choosing each leader depends on the peculiar circumstances surrounding each vacant position. There has been only one other leader of the church apart from the founder. He is the son of the leader himself. When his father died, there was a fierce succession contest. Some of the leaders of the church supported the founder's deputy while others supported the emergence of the founder's son. In the end, the founder's son was installed. After conceding the leadership of the church to the founder's son, the erstwhile deputy to the founder pulled out from the control of Ugbonla and proceeded to establish own church in his natal community. Some revered prophets and leaders of the church who had worked with the founder and held the view that the founder's deputy was most suited for the throne also pulled the local assemblies they headed out of Ugbonla's control and became independent. This gave impetus to the mass exodus of other smaller branches headed by ambitious leaders from Ugbonla's grip. In the branches, several factors account for the emergence of a leader or the successor to leadership. If in the founding of a church, the headquarters plays a significant role, the Oba could determine who is appointed as its head. If however, the establishment of the church is significantly powered by an individual or prophet, it is usually assumed the prophet would lead such an assembly. In the case of succession, depending on the organization of the church and how robust its structures are, its new leadership could be determined or influenced by the Oba in Ugbonla, by the local leadership

or by take-over by one of the supporters or followers/deputies to the departed leader.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: This is not usually the case but the chances of its occurrence cannot be completely ruled out. In the case of succession to the throne of Ugbonla, the founder was quoted to have said in one of his last sermons that the church would be led by his closest associate and deputy but the crown on his head belongs to his sons. By this, it was the opinion of those who supported the emergence of his erstwhile deputy that their founder had willed the church leadership to the deputy but had decided to make his sons succeed him on throne as the political leader of the community. This was however countered by those who supported the son that the community operates a theocracy. They maintained that the one who sits on the throne as king in the community must at the same time lead the church. Succession to church leadership at the branch level could be as intriguing and unpredictable as the narration of the emergence of Ugbonla's current leader.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: As described in the narration on the emergence of the current leader of the headquarters of the ministry, it is not usually the case that the leader's ministers choose the leader. A lot of factors come to play in the emergence of leaders and no two situations can be exactly the same.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

Notes: No single succession event plays out the same way as the other. The circumstances surrounding each case is one of the major factors that determines the emergence of a new leader

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: This may work in some circumstances but may not in others

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: This does not usually happen. Members of the congregation may have candidates to the throne which they support. They lend their support to the emergence of such individual. Depending on the local politics they may not always have significant roles to play in the actual succession events.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: This is not usually the case.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, those whose candidate(s) fails in their attempt to the throne act as opposition to the leadership of the church and may usually criticise the leader's actions. They continue to hold the leader as incapable of providing the acceptable level of leadership. In some cases, the leader may succeed in winning some of them over and thus enjoy relatively peaceful tenure of office.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Charges of fallibility against a leader almost never comes from his followers or supporters.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Such charges may come from those who desire the leadership position or others who supported the failed attempt of another person to the throne.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: When the leader of the church and political rulers in his region have unsettled differences, such political ruler may bring up charges against the church leader to discredit them or get at them. This is rumoured to have happened to the church leader in some recent past

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: There is no strict requirement on this but most disciples and followers of the leader often give full support to the leader's actions and decisions.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The community relies on the authority of the bible and hold it as the basis of their actions and belief system

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: The scripture they hold is the Holy Bible. They do not have a different story to the emergence of the Bible

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: No, their scriptures are not alterable

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: No formal institutions for interpreting the scriptures exist among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: No select group exists for transmitting the scriptures among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is the codified canon of Scriptures among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 5

Notes: The average space taken up by religious monument is less than 5% of the settlement total land mass

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1000

Notes: The community church is the largest single religious monument in ugbonla. It is approximately 1000 square meters. During important anniversaries or programmes of the church, the main floor and the gallery gets filled up before the spill over of the congregation spills over to the adjoining field around the church.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

Notes: The west tower of the community church is the tallest part of the community's religious monument. It is about 20 meters in height

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: The community does not have a dedicated cemetery for burying their dead. The standard practice is for families to bury their dead within their compound. Some of the tombs of late prominent prophets and leaders of the community serve as reference points and invokes nostalgia when community members who were alive during their days tell of the exploits of such prophets during their lifetime.

↳ Temples:

– No

Notes: There are no temples in Ugbonla community. The community church is the only religious worship centre in settlement.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: The only visible public altar in the community is the church where prayers and invocations are made. Aside this, members also offer prayers privately in their homes, church and other chosen locations. Such places where prayers and invocations hold are regarded as altars or platforms for engagement with the supreme being

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The most commonly used gathering point in Ugbonla is the church auditorium. There are other meeting points which include designated points in the king's palace, at the community beach, and other convenient points agreed upon by members

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Baptismal point at the community beach. This part of the river that flows through the northern boundary of Ugbonla serves as the place where members who have completed their theological training undergo their water baptism. The community conceives of water baptism as one of the cardinal pillars of faith which everyone must undergo to attain full membership status of the church.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: There are certain emblems, clothes and objects of devotion people wear and hang around their homes which are believed to serve different spiritual purposes. These include but not limited to wooden swords representing victory over enemies, wooden cross symbolising the power in the cross of Jesus and flags (white and red colours especially). These symbolise victory, peace and warfare.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In the C & S church of Zion, certain notable qualities in some species of animals are adopted when describing the deeds attributable to God. God is sometimes conceived as a lion, a hen etc. For example, "God will roar against your

enemies", "God will protect you as the hen covers her chicks under her wings" are used to describe the deeds of the supreme being and how he intervenes in the affairs of his followers.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In drawing from biblical examples of ascribing human qualities to the Judaic and Christian God, the C & S church of Zion ascribes human qualities like describing God as one with a mighty outstretched arms or referencing him as a mother who broods over her children. These and many examples of their conception of God as one who possesses human characteristics depicts them as a group which confers anthropomorphic qualities on their supreme being

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: God is sometimes also portrayed among the membership of the C & S church of Zion as the invisible yet ever present being who must be accorded all honour and reverence at all times

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The c & S church of Zion holds that there is an afterlife. They hold the belief that God rewards all humans with the afterlife they merit, either an afterlife of bliss or one of sorrow. People who have lived a life acceptable to their God would be rewarded with an afterlife of bliss while the wicked and unbelieving will inherit an afterlife of sorrow and wailing.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold the cross as a sacred symbol. To them, it represents the victory which Christ won for all of humanity. They also believe in the trinity and accept their sovereignty over them.

↳ Humans:

– No

Notes: The church does not hold any human as sacred neither do they ascribe any supernatural powers to any human except the divine powers granted their prophets and spiritual leaders by God. They often pray to the God of their founder and other leaders but their ultimate object of worship is their God.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, members who visit or live in Ugbonla take along with them, water energised by prophetic declarations in vessels, the earth of Ugbonla or some other symbolic and tangible objects to anoint their loved ones who are incapacitated but for which a divine intervention is sought. In spite of their inability to visit Ugbonla by themselves, there are stories of a change in their conditions or experiences once they establish contact with the spiritually energised objects.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Some sacred sites in Ugbonla community include the church grounds, the mausoleum and the baptismal arena

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The baptismal arena is the only sacred site in Ugbonla associated with the element of water believed to possess divine powers to heal the sick, raise the dead and wrought other interventions in the life of those specifically instructed to have a bath in it.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: Pilgrimages to Israel, the Christian's holy land is rare and not obligatory. The founder and notable prophets went on pilgrimage to Israel during his lifetime. However, pilgrimages to Ugbonla by members residing outside the community is mandatory. They are expected to attend conventions, anniversaries and other important convocations. Besides, no one who becomes a full member of the church will acquire such status without their completion of the theological training which holds in Ugbonla from July to December biennially.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: In the C & S church of Zion, the human spirit is believed to be distinct from the body. They hold fast to the saying that flesh and blood shall not inherit the kingdom of heaven but the spirit alone. Hence the teaching among them that the human spirit must be well nourished with the word of God as espoused in the bible so the spirit could be prepared to enter the blissful afterlife

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, the human spirit-mind is conceived as non-material among the C & S church of Zion. However, they also hold that when the afterlife commences, the spirits of the saints would be housed in a material frame which shall never suffer corruption or death. Likewise, the spirit-mind of those who will inherit eternal doom will also be housed in a frame which shall make them capable of feeling and suffering the pains and anguish of the torment they shall ceaselessly encounter in the afterlife.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The C & S church of Zion hold that the body is the vehicle which the spirit needs to carry out divine mandates. The body should be trained to be subject to the needs and wellbeing of the spirit and not otherwise. If the body is indulged above the spirit, then an afterlife of doom and anguish may just be awaiting the spirit which dwelled in that body

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Among the C & S church of Zion, two distinct spaces exist where the afterlife would be enjoyed or endured. One is the blissful afterlife in a space above the earth, The other is the gloomy and unpalatable afterlife somewhere beneath the earth.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: There is a clear theology about the afterlife "above" among the C & S church of Zion community

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Notes: There is a clear theology on the afterlife "below" among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: There is no concept of an "horizontal" afterlife among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: The concept of the afterlife among the C & S church of Zion is well defined. They have a clear theology surrounding the direction or location of their afterlife. Both afterlife which they conceive in their world of imagination are in well defined spaces; above and beneath.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: They agree that it is appointed unto man to die once and after death comes judgement. However, in their informal discussions, some of them entertain the idea of reincarnation. This could happen when an individual dies young and then they begin another life in a location where they are not known in their previous life.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Corpses of adherents are treated with utmost dignity. The community could hold a memorial service for the dead while the corpse is laid in state. After this, the church leaders lead the corpse's committal to mother earth signifying the end of the life of the individual

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Once the burial takes place, all relations with the dead ceases.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No grave goods accompany the corpse. The point that all mortals came to the world empty and without any substance and that all mortals will return same way influences the practice of burying the corpse with no grave goods among the C & S church of Zion members.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: Most people in Ugbonla bury their dead within their family compounds

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: In Ugbonla, there are homes where corpses are buried beneath the rooms used by the deceased during their lifetime. Some other choose any location of their choice within their homes to bury their dead.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Since the founding of Ugbonla, only the founder was buried in a special way. His remains were interred in a mausoleum beside the church and has remained a tourist attraction in the community. Some folks pray by the tomb while other leave their prayer requests and other emblems there for periods of time in other to have their desires on their challenging issues met.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: To the extent that the supreme being (God) worshipped in Ugbonla is attributed to possess feelings like humans, feels betrayed, has eyes which scan through the earth, hands which are mighty to deliver from the vicissitudes of life, he can be said to possess anthropomorphic characteristics. This is the extent that their conception of God as

being anthropomorphic ends

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion perceive their supreme deity to be resident up in the sky. Several reference is made to the abode of their supreme being in the heavens in their scriptures. He is reputed to have made his abode in heaven as he made the earth his footstool.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The supreme being worshipped among the C & S church of Zion is never conceived of as of the underworld. He is seen as dwelling in light unapproachable.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The supreme being worshipped among the C & S church of Zion is distinct from their king. He is not merged or equated with the king by any stretch of their imagination.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The monarch is seen as completely human but a very important vessel in the hands of the high god to bring the will of the supreme being to men and women in the world.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is seen among the C & S church of Zion as belonging to a class to whom no other being shares. He is conceived of as one without genealogy, without kin or kith but the originator of all there is. He was not created but created all things. He was not formed but he formed all things.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: In the C & S church of Zion, the supreme high god belongs to a class that he shares with no other being.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god is unquestionably good and that

there is no evil whatsoever in him.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god among the C & S church of Zion is all good, all knowing, all powerful, benevolent, gracious, full of compassion and never failing.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The knowledge of the supreme high god about the world is limitless. He created the world and so is familiar with all that is in it.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The knowledge of the supreme high god about the world is limitless. He created the entire world and so is familiar with all that is in it.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Not only is the knowledge of the supreme high god unrestricted within the sample region, his knowledge of the entire world is limitless

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the C & S church of Zion believe that the knowledge of the supreme high god is unrestricted outside the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god sees everyone everywhere at every time.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god sees everyone everywhere at every time.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god sees inside the heart/mind and observes the hidden motives of all beings.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god knows the basic character and personal essence of every being.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god knows what will happen to everyone and what every being will do in the future. The scriptures (bible) alludes to this attribute of the supreme high god.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god has other knowledge of this world which no human knows. Some of the other knowledge outside the ones already mentioned which the supreme high god has include the knowledge of all events happening everywhere in the world at the same time without losing essential facts about those taking place in one location at the expense of others in other places and locations. He is seen as all knowing.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion belief that the supreme high god knows the intentions and motivations behind the actions of every mortal being and so able to reward everyone according to their intentions.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The church hold that true and just rewards are only received from the supreme high god as he cannot be deceived by any being. He rewards according to the intentions of the heart.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that just as the supreme high god can reward, it is also right and justifiable for him to be able to punish. He is seen as the perfect one to give appropriate punishment for the wrong doing of every being.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is seen among the C & S church of Zion as having direct causal efficacy in the world

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the supreme high god exhibits positive emotion. He is capable of being joyous, pleased with humans, satisfied with the conduct of humans etc

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is also believed to exhibit negative emotions whenever he is displeased or angered by humans. He can be said to change his mind concerning the good he had purposed to do to humans when they no longer merit it by their unfaithfulness or disobedience.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god never suffers hunger for food. He is conceived as one who is not sustained by physical food

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: No other supernatural being is to be worshipped by the members of the C & S church of Zion. They hold their high god as the only one deserving of worship and reverence.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The C & S church of Zion believe that the supreme being is extremely deep and can never be known fully by the limited capacity and knowledge of the human intellect.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in waking and everyday life

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in dreams

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in trance possession

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in divination. Their divination practice is through prayers and supplication. The church comes to the knowledge of the supreme being's will when they pray and supplicate.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Each member of the church can approach the supreme being by themselves and communicate with him. He listens to and grants the requests of each member. Although the religious specialists could also intervene in difficult situations that individual members cannot solve by themselves.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The monarch is not the only person able or permitted to speak to the supreme being on behalf of the member. Every member has the opportunity to go before the supreme being by themselves.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme being also communicates with the living through the bible, through circumstances and through everyday occurrences.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Before the occupancy of Ugbonla by the C & S church of Zion, the geographical space called Ugbonla today was notorious for being the dumpsite for corpses of persons associated with evil acts and lunatics. In many African cultures, it is held that spirits occupy every space. They are ever present and their presence felt by the spiritually inclined. They hold territories and determine the direction of occurrences in the physical realm. Therefore, as Ugbonla was previously the final resting home to evil personalities and lunatics, the spirits controlling the land would naturally be those with evil tendencies. So these human spirits previously occupied the space which the community had to contend with so fiercely.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Occasionally, human spirits could be seen by the spiritually inclined, especially the prophets. This happens when a situation which demands special attention is required. It may be that evil forces are already progressing with terminating the life of a victim whom God desires to deliver from imminent death or danger, during the pendency of such final calamity, prophets could be energised or empowered to see in the realm of the spirit the situation and lead a spiritual battle to remedy the situation.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Most times, the presence of human spirits in Ugbonla is physically felt by prophets and other members with sharp spiritual sensitivity.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: The idea or concept of knowledge attributable to human spirit in Ugbonla could be viewed from two perspectives. One is the idea regarding spirits of those evil persons who had lived in the past but who still populate the terrestrial space. The knowledge of these spirits could be restricted to the domain of human affairs they are interested in or to those exposed to in their previous existence. Secondly, the human spirits inhabiting the prophets though naturally limited are given access to the infinite realm of knowing both in time (past, present and future) and space (without geographical limitations). By this ability which the prophets possess, they spontaneously relate with the world of the spirit and intervene in matters for which they are prompted.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of evil individuals who previously walked the area could be limited to the area and to the individuals they knew while they physically lived in the area. However, spirits of the prophets are not strictly limited especially when they begin to operate in the prophetic office. One of the importance of the prophetic ministry is to neutralise the impact and control of the evil forces controlling their physical space and to free humans of their negative impact. A prophet who previously knew nothing of the circumstances surrounding an individual's life could be given access through a trance, a vision, a dream or other means so as to use the facts deduced to help the individual escape from the forces inhibiting their progress.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This is partially true. It is true only with regards to the ability of the spirits of the prophets and those who are spiritually empowered to intervene in some circumstances or situations relating to a member who needs to be set free from the negative influence of evil forces

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Again this only applies to the spirits of the prophets who may be granted unrestricted access to know and understand events, situations and occurrences outside their sample region. The need for this is usually for their positive intervention in the situation which they have come to understand by the means of their spiritual ability.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Naturally, the spirits of the evils folks (either the living or dead evil folks) can see almost everyone they want to harm. Their capability to see or harm their targets could only be restricted or inhibited by the superior spiritual powers of the spirits of the prophets. However, the spirits of the prophets may only be activated to see human spirits everywhere in public if there is an intervention the supreme being desires they accomplish over the life of the person whose spirit has become visible to them

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Naturally, the human spirits associated with evil folks can see their target everywhere whether in the light, in the dark, far or near. When the prophets are also being energised to operate in their office, they can see human spirits they are required to assist without any inhibition or restriction. They can see human spirits of those who are physically living in a different continent from them.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, this is true for the spirits inhabiting evil folks and the prophets. They can see the plans and contemplations and hidden motives in the heart/mind of their target.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the spirits of evil folks and those of the prophets know the basic character or personal essence of their target

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, this is very true in the imagination of the members of the C & S church of Zion. Human spirits of evil folks and those of the prophets are held as having the capacity to know future events

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: By their access to the metaphysical (spiritual) realm, spirits of the prophets and the evil persons access knowledge which are not available to the average individual

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, the C & S church of Zion hold that human spirits are agents or enforcers of the law of karma. When an individual lives an upright and devoted life to God, the supreme being ensured they are protected from the wandering evil human spirits. The supreme being would always ensure they are protection sovereignly or could prompt the prophets to secure them in other circumstances.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Just as human spirits - operating in prophets - can reward, (that is, be instruments for ensuring no evil overtakes the kind and pious folks) human spirits (operating in evil persons; dead or alive) could also be instruments for punishing humans for wrongs and their evil deeds. These spirits act as instruments for reward for good as well as for evil deeds amongst men.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: At times, spirits, just like humans could be acting with their best intentions but ignorantly fulfilling the law of karma. They inadvertently serve rewards for both good and evil deeds exercised in the past

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: This is a notion held in the C & S church of Zion. Human spirits which operate in prophets and other spiritual mediums as well as those which inhabit the evil personalities have a memory and could sometimes state their justification for acting in a manner they have chosen or for pursuing a chosen course of action.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, human spirits exhibit positive emotions. They sometimes empathise, feel sorry for individuals who are undergoing attacks from spiritual forces and could experience frustrations trying unsuccessfully to help ameliorate their situation.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Just as good human spirits (like those operating in prophets) exhibit positive emotions, they also display negative emotions or show rage when confronted with evil forces who according to their estimation unjustly attack innocent persons. Evil spiritual forces may also exhibit negative emotions when they are unable to perform their evil intentions on their targets but keep failing and suffering defeat.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, human spirits possess hunger but the kind of hunger they possess may not be that requiring the satisfaction of physical appetite of food but that of vengeance or recompense for good or bad deeds. They enforce the law of karma and are quite passionate in their quest for satisfying this ambition.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Human spirits are capable of exhibiting several emotions outside of those specific ones highlighted above. They could display their frustrations like expression of anger and are capable of celebrating their successes. The list of other emotions or features they possess is endless.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The medium of communicating with the living is entirely at the discretion of the spirits. They may choose this medium or others as they deem appropriate.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The medium of communicating with the living is entirely at the discretion of the spirits. They may choose this medium or others as they deem appropriate.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The medium of communicating with the living is entirely at the discretion of the spirits. They may choose this medium or others as they deem appropriate.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: The medium of communicating with the living is entirely at the discretion of the spirits. They may choose this medium or others as they deem appropriate. This is just one of the mediums they use to relate to humans.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: The medium of communicating with the living is entirely at the discretion of the spirits. They may choose this medium or others as they deem appropriate. Though they speak through specialists, this is not the only means by which they reach the people.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The medium of communicating with the living is entirely at the discretion of the spirits. They may choose this medium or others as they deem appropriate. They are not restricted to communicating to the people through their monarchs.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: The means by which the human spirits communicate with the living could be said to be inexhaustible.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings are ever present but never seen by almost all the the people who populate the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla. It is only on rare occasions that they are seen by the prophets and those they will to reveal themselves to .

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: The presence of the supernatural beings in religious gatherings in the C & S church of Zion is usually not felt the way a human's presence is felt. Their presence could be explained in abstract terms or through their actions or manifestations in their meetings. They could energise the prophets to perform extra-ordinary spiritual feats or cause mighty acts of deliverance from strong spiritual bondages to be experienced.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The knowledge of supernatural beings about the domain of human affairs among the C & S church of Zion is universal and unrestricted.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The knowledge of non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion is not restricted to any specific area within or outside the sample region

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge of non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion is not restricted to any specific area within the sample region

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge of non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion is not restricted to any area outside the sample region

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion can see humans and other elements everywhere normally visible and in public

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion can see humans and other elements everywhere in the dark or at home

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion can see inside the heart. They can see the contemplations of the mind and other hidden motives

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion know the basic character (personal essence) of all mortals.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion know what will happen to all mortals in future and what each person will do later in their life

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion have other knowledge of this world. They know about every other thing men are not bothered about because they brought all things into existence.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion can reward every good action and intention.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion can punish every evil or negative action and intention.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Since they control significantly all courses and directions of events, supernatural beings monitor the actions of men and ensure justice for every action taken. The resultant effect of all actions undertaken by mortals therefore is that they receive a reward justifiable to their actions. The supernatural beings therefore ensure the lot of the righteous is splendid and those of the evil is reflective of their deeds.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings express satisfaction, joy and fulfilment when their desires are accomplished.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion are capable of showing displeasure when their wishes and desires are temporarily unmet because the human component which should serve as vehicles for fulfilling their desires fail to fulfil their side of the equation necessary for the anticipated results.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion possess hunger for an equitable recompense for the actions of each mortal. They do not eat food nor drink fluids as required of men.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The supernatural beings among the C & S church of Zion possess and exhibit some other features not directly mentioned previously. They are conceived as

warriors, yet loving, faithful, honest, protective, compassionate among other qualities

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The concept of mixed human-divine beings does not exist among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The most important supernatural being the church believes in is the God of the Christian Bible. This God however manifested through His Son; Jesus Christ and now through the Holy Spirit who deploys angels to fulfil his desires among men.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural monitors the observance of prosocial norms among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla. They believe that all human acts on the earth are visible before the eyes of the supernatural being. No one can therefore keep secrets of wrongdoing from him

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: There are no strict food taboos among the C & S church of Zion Ugbonla community

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Most grounds and places in Ugbonla are accessible to everyone. The only exception is the church altar where women are not allowed access to. They are not

even allowed to clean it up. They must seek the assistance of a man to help them with anything they require from the altar

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a number of sacred objects among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla. There are specified ways of handling most of them, usually by specialised handlers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The supernatural being who is at the centre of worship among the C & S church of Zion is conceived as one who cares about every aspect of the lives of the people.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In fact murder is a grave offence in the Zion community. It has to be investigated and those guilty must face the consequences of their actions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of any individual is a grave offence

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Among the C & S church of Zion, no human life is to be taken by another

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: premarital sex was once strongly condemned just as adultery but premarital sex is fast becoming a misdemeanour the community has learnt to tolerate

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the C & S church of Zion are strongly encouraged to speak the truth at all times. They hold the believe that no liar shall partake of God's after life promises except they turn from their ways

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Oath taking is a very serious spiritual exercise. All parties to the oath must ensure that they fulfil their own side of the bargain to avoid unpleasant experiences.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings in Ugbonla care about laziness and slothfulness. They frown at it a lot

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings care about sorcery. They either set their captives free or face a tough time with the prophets

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Fighting of any sort is forbidden among the C & S church of Zion

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural being to which the C & S church of Zion identify does not shirk risk neither does it look kindly at his followers doing same. When a duty is handed to any of his followers in the church, it is done in the firm belief that the supernatural who is all knowing and all powerful has endowed the fellow with all powers and conditions necessary to fulfil the mandate. Hence, it brings disappointment to God when such task is evaded, avoided or haphazardly done.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Elders are held in high esteem among the C & S church of Zion congregation. The traditional culture of the Ilaje, and indeed the entire Yoruba race accords significant respect to elders

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural being to whom the C & S church of Zion hold allegiance disapproves so strongly of gossip.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion members are constantly reminded of the ten commandments, one of which states that you shall not covet your neighbour's property, his wife or any of his belongings. It is strongly against the teachings and beliefs of the C & S church of Zion to engage in property crime

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are meant to be followed strictly and reverently. This is the understanding of the church and they hold strongly to the fact that their rituals are only going to be acceptable to the supreme being if they are observed in the prescribed way

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: In order for the supplications of the members of the C & S church of Zion members to be heard and responded to by the supreme being, the people hold firmly to the condition that the appropriate rituals must be performed in the prescribed manner

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: The church devotes much time and efforts in proclaiming its message of good news and urges others still living outside of what they consider as the ideal way/path to join them on their path to bliss and fulfilment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The need to be fair, just and honest in business is at the core of the message of the church. They teach and admonish their members in business never to seek opportunity to exploit others while transacting business

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: The church is always mindful of good hygiene practices. The Ugbonla community has times set aside for community work aimed at keeping their environment clean. They encourage members to observe good personal hygiene all the time.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The supernatural being whom the C & S church of Zion worships cares about the successes, prosperity, good health and general wellbeing of the members. They must however conduct themselves in accordance with the general conditions set out to merit the support they need to succeed.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The high god may choose to undertake the task of retribution to errant members himself or decide to allow other agents he permits to deal with those who deserve punishment for their mis/deeds

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: There is only one all-knowing and all-powerful supernatural being recognised in the C & S church of Zion. Other beings are simply participants or players who act directly or inadvertently to fulfil the divine mandate. This being directs and controls all forces and each action undertaken by both the good and evil forces are moderated or permitted by this all powerful force in fulfilment of the law of nature and law of karma.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: The cause-effect principle is not seen as a naturally flowing occurrence or coincidence among the C & S church of Zion. The church holds that the cause-effect principle is sustained by the all-powerful and all-knowing divine being who ensures that this principle is kept in place.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Notes: The church holds that the divine being alone sustains and keeps the cause-effect principle from failing.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Notes: This is not often the reason for punishments as much as the need to be fair and just in all areas of life. When members are honest, live a life devoid of offence to fellow men and God, they stand a chance to enjoy relative peace and progress in their ways. Punishments, more often, come as the a result of the efficacy of the law of Karma

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: When a person within the congregation known to have gone contrary to group norms suffers a misfortune, has an ailment or is observed to be having some difficulty in one area of life, such predicament is adjudged to be the consequence of their misdeeds. Others therefore see the situation as a punishment for the wrongs done by the fellow. They then see reasons not to go contrary to group norms to avoid similar misfortune or calamity

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the C & S church of Zion are admonished to shun selfishness as it hampers group cohesion, foster greed and promotes avarice. So, selfishness is one of the offenses for which an individual may be punished or sanctioned in Ugbonla and the religious community it represents.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Punishment for selfishness may not only be received randomly. It could come through the instrumentality of the enforcement of the law of karma or be spoken against publicly or privately to any fellow found guilty of it.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishment for selfishness as with other misdemeanours may be conceived as been served on those guilty of it by some abstract or philosophical explanations. For example, it is taught among the Ugbonla community that what an individual greedily acquires or selfishly accrues is all their eyes could conceive. However, a lot more which they could have benefitted from would be kept off their grip by the supernatural being who only tested them with the little they saw and held on to. If they exhibited the virtue of selflessness, more would have been divinely channelled their way, and they would have been better off by the latter. It is a purer gift and is meant to profit them more.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The greatest punishment in afterlife for disobedience to divine command among the C & S church of Zion is a lifetime in Hades or hell. It is a place of torment and grieve.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: No, punishment in the afterlife consists of gross sensory displeasure which includes burning forever in a fire of unimaginable flames.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife consists of gross sensory displeasure which includes burning forever in a fire of unimaginable flames.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: The C & S church of Zion does not hold the notion of reincarnation in an inferior life form for the purpose of eternal damnation and punishment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: The C & S church of Zion does not hold the notion of reincarnation in an inferior life form for the purpose of eternal damnation and punishment.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: There are other forms of torment for those who would suffer the fate of eternal punishment in the theology of the C & S church of Zion. This includes the torment of sores, deadly insect infestation, an unending cycle of burns in an unquenchable fire among others.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion holds that no good deed or wrongdoing goes without

an appropriate pay back or recompense in this world and in the afterlife from supernatural being who controls the visible and invisible world.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, "bad luck" could be used to describe the experience of those undergoing punishments for wrong doings in this life but the church would see it more as not just a matter of ill luck but a well deserved reward for wrong steps previously taken for which the divine powers are holding the fellow to account and ensuring a just recompense for their actions.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion may attribute political failures indeed to the many offenses or wrongdoing of the citizenry and call on everyone to repent of their wrongdoings so the divine could usher in a season of refreshing and political stability.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of defeat in battle as a punishment in this life could be stretched to other forms of disappointments like business losses, marriage failures, death of a loved one, untimely death and other misfortunes. The C & S church of Zion attributes misfortunes generally to attacks from the enemy or divine judgement.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: For the Ilaje who populate the C & S church of Zion Ugbonla, punishment for wrongdoing also extends to poor catch in the rivers and the Atlantic ocean. This is because as riparian folks or sea farers, their major occupation is fishing.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: The church could rationalise any misfortune including auto crashes, boat mishap or other forms of accident to either the divine powers or the evil forces. Such could either be seen as a punishment from the supernatural being or an attack from evil forces.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Ailment, sickness, or any sensory displeasures could be rationalised as punishment for wrongdoing among the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: When viewed from the perspective of the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla, extreme sensory displeasure could be viewed as punishment for wrongdoing. Prayer altars could be raised for folks suffering from such discomfort to ameliorate their condition. However, this is not the only possible reason for the cause of such suffering.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is perfectly in order with the theology of the C & S church of Zion to rationalise sicknesses or illnesses as punishments in this life for the disobedience or wrongdoing of members or other people in general.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is perfectly in order with the theology of the C & S church of Zion to rationalise impaired reproduction as punishments in this life for the disobedience or wrongdoing of members or other people in general.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is perfectly in order with the theology of the C & S church of Zion to rationalise bad luck visited on descendants as punishments in this life for the disobedience or wrongdoing of parents, members or other people in general.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Among the C & S church of Zion, misfortunes or evil occurrences of diverse forms could be rationalised punishments for wrongdoing. This includes but not limited to job losses, strange and unexplainable catastrophic events like the Covid-19 pandemic etc

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The cause or purpose of supernatural rewards could be executed by the high god or any other agent his chooses.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The C & S church of Zion belief that supernatural reward is done by the supreme being alone. Other beings are simply participants or players who act directly or inadvertently to fulfil the divine mandate. This being directs and controls all forces and each action undertaken by both the good and evil forces are moderated or permitted by this all powerful force in fulfilment of the law of nature and law of karma.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: According to the C & S church of Zion, supernatural rewards are not achieved through impersonal cause-effect principle. Supernatural rewards are not seen as naturally flowing occurrences or coincidences among the C & S church of Zion. The church holds that the cause-effect principle is sustained by the all-powerful and all-knowing divine being who ensures that this principle is kept in place.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, supernatural rewards have a way of encouraging religious ritual-devotional adherence among the membership of the C & S church of Zion. When an individual is perceived to have suffered some misfortune after undertaking an act which the community frowns at, such fellow would be seen as suffering the consequences of their actions. Subsequently, others are better advised that there are consequences for behaviours considered unacceptable among the people. Others shun such actions in the future.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: When the community establishes that an individual or group has undertaken actions that contravene community norms, if penalties are spelt out against such actions in their laws, it becomes necessary to invoke the penalties or sanctions. When this is done, it sends a message to others that group norms are meant to be observed and adhered to.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Selfishness is one attribute the community frowns at. This is because it does not foster the collective interest. When selfishness is perceived to have been responsible for the actions of an individual or group of people in Ugbonla or the C & S church of Zion generally, there are bound to be sanctions on those identified with such actions.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Rewards are not usually meted out randomly in the C & S church of Zion. They

are usually purposefully administered to encourage patriotism and discourage unpatriotic acts.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In fact, this is a major motivation for the continuous piety of many among the C & S church of Zion. The idea of a grand and final reward in the hereafter keeps many in the faith and hoping for bliss in the life to come.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches sensory pleasures as reward for observance of group norms in the afterlife. Access to nourishing fruits, pleasures of peaceful flowing rivers and music from well coordinated angelic orchestra are a few of the sensory pleasures the people hope to be treated to in the life to come.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church generally teaches all forms of sensory pleasures as reward for observance of group norms in the afterlife. In addition to access to nourishing fruits, pleasures of peaceful flowing rivers and music from well coordinated angelic orchestra which the people hope to be treated to in the life to come, there is also the pleasure of ruling over nations, exercising dominion over peoples and having all of one's desires met. The good lot of the faithful among the C & S church of Zion is actually endless.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Undiluted and endless happiness is a promise for those who stay faithful to the teachings of the C & S church of Zion in the afterlife.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation to a superior life form is not the real description of the afterlife experience of the C & S church of Zion. In stead, the same people will only put on an incorruptible body after putting off this corruptible frame.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation in a superior realm is not the real description of the afterlife experience of the C & S church of Zion. In stead, the same people will only put on an incorruptible body after putting off this corruptible frame.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: It is held among the C & S church of Zion that all things will be made new. The emphasis is on all things, This means that all conceivable and unconceivable matters will take on new forms of bliss and satisfaction. The joy and satisfaction is said to be comparable to none of the earthly experience.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The biblical saying that "Be not deceived, whatsoever any man sows, that he shall receive" is highly emphasised among the C & S church of Zion. This type of supernatural reward is both available and to be benefitted from both now and in the life to come

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: In the strict sense, the reward accruable to members for the way they choose to conduct themselves is not conceived as good or bad luck. It is a standard and incontrovertible recompense they deserve either in this life or in that which is to come. Therefore, the people must undertake good acts to receive good rewards and vice versa.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they conceive the rewards they receive in this life to include a lot of good things of which political success or power is a part. Although they do not seek political power as a group, they have supported political actors in the past and mobilised support for them within and outside of their religious group. When those they support for political offices gain power, they are happy. However, the church has never been seen to be against the idea of political organisations or be in support of insurrection.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: They conceive rewards in this life to consist of success not only in battles but in all their endeavours.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: They conceive rewards in this life to consist of peace and stability in their private and group existence as well as the entire human polity.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: They conceive rewards in this life to consist of healthy crops, good weather, great catch of fish, healthy and prosperous children among other things.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: They conceive rewards in this life to consist of success in journeys and safety everywhere.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: They conceive rewards in this life to consist of mild sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: They conceive rewards in this life to consist of extreme sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion consider enhanced health as a reward for uprightness in this life. They hold the saying of the bible "... with long life will I satisfy you" as a potent promise for them.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Enhanced reproductive success is yet another reward the C & S church of Zion hold as their inalienable right. They are quick to mention the biblical promise of children surrounding their table as a reward from the divine personality.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the C & S church of Zion see the rewards of fortune on the descendants as their entitlement. They say God's promises are to them and their children to the third and fourth generations.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The array of good rewards for the uprightness of the members of the C & S church of Zion is inexhaustible. All manners of rewards including unexplainable escape from danger and death are included in the rewards they lay claim to.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The messianic beliefs which the C & S church of Zion hold is centred on Jesus Christ. They hold that he has perfected the work of redemption and has given mankind the opportunity for bliss in the afterlife if they follow the path to redemption which he opened up to humanity

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The messiah's whereabouts is known. He is said to be in the skyey heavens making provision to receive all those who belief in him at a time the supreme being alone will sanction.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: The Messiah is said to be alive, albeit in a realm outside of this world. The C & S church of Zion belief in Jesus as the Messiah. They agree that he walked this earth more than 2000 years ago. He has completed his work of redemption and has gone up the skyey heavens to prepare a place for all those who abide by his teachings. He is coming sometime in the future, at a time when no one knows to take with him all those who abide by his teachings. The C & S church of Zion hold themselves apart as a church which follows his teachings and abide by his admonitions

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the messiah will come sometime soon in this lifetime to harvest the godly to an abode of peace and bliss.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: Though the messiah is coming to take with him his faithful followers at a time in the future, however, the date and time of his coming is not known to anyone.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the messiah's return is certain but the time of his coming is not known to anyone.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: According to the C & S church of Zion, the time of the coming of the messiah is unknown. However, his coming is not in the distant future.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: The return of the messiah is still a future event. He is being expected by the C & S church of Zion.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Notes: The C & S church of Zion belief in the existence of one messiah; Jesus Christ. No messiah came before him and none will arise after him.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The messiah's purpose is well defined among the people of the C & S church of Zion. They hold the belief that he came to save humanity from depravity and eternal separation caused by humankind's disobedience to God.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: The focus of the messiah is the spiritual liberation of humanity and not the acquisition of political power or rule to any people.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion hold that the messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions and encourages humanity to seek truth and follow the noble path.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Though his overriding reason for undertaking the messianic task is to bring spiritual blessings to humanity, the C & S church of Zion also hold that he came with a full package for humanity. He gives physical blessings, restores health and brings healing as well as keeping those who belief in him from the evil one.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion belief that certain events will take place at the close of this age. According to them, death is the final end of humankind. There shall be judgement and an eternal abode of the spirit and soul of all humankind

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: The church holds that this lifetime will end after which an end shall come to existence here before a new order will emerge through the design and programme of the supernatural being

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that eschaton is a future event

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: In the belief and teachings of the C & S church of Zion, eschaton is a future event which would take place at an unspecified time in the near future.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: In the belief and teachings of the C & S church of Zion, eschaton is a future event which would take place at an unspecified time in the near future. Several portions of the bible which the church holds as valid posits of the imminent return of the messiah in the near future. One of such portions of the bible says "... behold, I come quickly"

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Notes: To the church, eschaton is a series of events which shall happen in the near future

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the church hold that the bible instructs them to preach the word of the messiah to all of humanity. Once they preach and everyone has had the opportunity to listen to the gospel, the end shall come

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that there shall be a last judgement where everyone shall give account of what they had done while in the flesh. Once this is done, those who were found upright shall begin an eternal life in bliss while those who were condemned by the supernatural being shall begin an unending life and pain, sorrow, anguish and deprivation.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

Notes: The world shall not be restored but it shall pass away or be consumed by fire. The C & S church of Zion belief that the current world shall pass away and a new shall emerge. They allude to the bible as their authority in matters such as this

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that for a limited time (millennial reign) when the messiah and his followers return to the earth to exhibit a sample of the bliss God intended for human kind ,the earth shall be peaceful. This will only be a temporal event before the final judgement.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

Notes: The messiah the C & S church of Zion professes is not a political messiah but essentially a religious one, His main duty and profession is that he saves people from their sins.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: The establishment of a new religious system is not the focus of the messiah professed by the C & S church of Zion. Rather he came to fulfill the law and the prophets.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Those who follow the messiah's teachings shall survive the eschaton and be ushered into bliss and glory

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Only the upright members of the church and other upright folks everywhere shall survive the eschaton

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion belief that the subset of the members of the church which shall survive the eschaton shall be those who follow strictly the way set by the

messiah. Other individuals outside the church who meet this condition for surviving the eschaton shall also enjoy the rare privilege of reigning with the messiah.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Those who will survive the eschaton shall be those who follow strictly the admonitions of the messiah.

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The church holds that only those who are obedient to God through his messiah shall survive the eschaton

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: No other survival conditions exist by which any human can survive the eschaton except through the messiah.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group prescribes general social norms for her members

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Ugbonla community upholds universal principles of morality and teaches strict adherence to group norms which are not different from the ideals of most societies.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion carefully adopts, keeps and teaches the several virtues advocated in the bible. The community of the virtues which the community teaches include faith, love, patience, perseverance, endurance and selflessness. It also emphasises on kindness, peaceful coexistence, cleanness and righteousness toward God.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: These are some of the virtues the community beliefs in.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: The battle here may be the day to day resolution to achieve one's dreams. The community holds the view that to be alive daily is a victory over death and to keep pressing forward and achieving one's dreams is yet another battle that must be fought daily and won. However, there is a bigger battle which the evil forces bring our way daily and this is not just a factor of the way a person lives their life. Such battles come the way of good and evil folks. The good people have a better chance of subduing the evil forces as the law of karma stands in their favour. Most importantly, they hold the belief as they reference in the bible that God would not allow the lot of the wicked to rest on the portion of the righteous. Chances that evil people will be subdued by their battles are however higher giving the fact that evil pursues the wicked just as karma will visit and catch up with them someday. This is reason why the church admonishes their members to keep doing good all the time.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches her members to be courageous in the face of challenges and battles. According to them, a feeble hearted folk is naturally positioned to fall and be conquered by the challenges of life.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: To the C & S church of Zion members, the importance of compassion, empathy, kindness and benevolence cannot be over emphasised. The church teaches her members to exercise and exhibit these virtues in all situations.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: The church beliefs in the importance of mercy, forgiveness and tolerance and teaches her members to imbibe them and exercise the virtues always.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Generosity and charity are key attributes the church admonishes her members to inculcate. In fact, most of the church programmes are executed through the generous giving of the members. They also carry out charitable acts constantly.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: The church beliefs firmly in the virtues of selflessness and selfless giving. They are careful to demonstrate it in their daily living and not just in theory.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: Righteousness is a cardinal virtue the C & S church of Zion beliefs in. They hold the view that their prayers and supplications would not be answered if they neglect righteous living.

Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: The church beliefs strongly in the potency of ritual purity, ritual adherence and abstention from sources of impurity as they conduct themselves in their private and public life. The members of the C & S church of Zion hold the view that strict adherence to instructions on issues of ritual purity, compliance with ritual guidelines and remaining ritually pure are key ingredients to the success of their ritual observances.

Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches the virtues of respectfulness and courtesy and encourages members to live by them.

Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches the virtues of familial obedience. They hold that our total and unconditional submission goes to God first. On the second hand, we also owe our parents and elders filial piety. When obedience to our parents challenges our total submission to God, we must choose to honour God and politely and courteously request our parents' understanding. The church encourages members to live by these principles.

Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Fidelity and loyalty are taught and encouraged among members of the C & S church of Zion. Sexual purity and loyalty to one's spouse are taken as very important ingredients to a healthy family and healthy community.

Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches on need for cooperation within groups, in homes, schools, at work and in all areas.

Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: The church upholds the necessity of independence of every individual. It advocates for creativity in business and the execution of assignments and beliefs in the personal liberty and freedom of all individual members. It however teaches that independence, creativity and freedom must be exercised with maturity and caution to avoid the pitfalls that come with lack of restraint and their abuse.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes in and teaches the virtues of moderation and frugality in all things.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: Forbearance, fortitude and patience are key features of the church teachings and beliefs. Members are encouraged to exhibit these virtues in all they do

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches diligence, self-discipline and excellence. Members are taught to inculcate the discipline of excellence, pursue diligence in their daily tasks and exhibit self-discipline always

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: C & S church of Zion teaches her members to be assertive and hold their ground against sin, evil and ungodliness. The church impresses on her members to be decisive and confident in their ability to do make impact as well as demonstrate initiative in executing tasks.

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: Members of the church are taught to be strong not just physically but emotionally, psychologically and spiritually.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: The church's attitude towards power shows that individuals should not be overtly ambitious for it. Members should see power as vested in the supreme being who gives it to whomsoever they will. Everyone who has been given the privilege of being in position of power, influence and authority will give account on the last day how they dispensed of it. Concerning status and nobility, the church recognises their existence but also holds the view that as much as they are conferred on certain people by lineage and circumstances of birth, they should not make one proud, haughty or pompous.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches humility and modesty and encourages members to imbibe and live by them

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches members the virtue of contentment, advises they maintain uphold serenity and calmness at all times. It also emphasises on the discipline of equanimity in all situations.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: The benefits inherent in being joyful, enthusiastic and cheerful are endless. The church admonishes members to allow the joy of the lord strengthen them as well as encouraging themselves as being capable and able to do all things through Christ who strengthens them. They are taught never to allow anything rob them of their joy or steal their peace.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: This is a central virtue the church holds. Their idea of eschatology is deeply embedded in hope of a reward that will come as a result of their restraint in this life.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds to the view that a grateful heart receives more for expressing gratitude for a favour received.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that human reverence should be to the supreme being first and then to constituted authority. Members of the church are taught to be in awe of the wonders of creation which they believe was executed by the supernatural being which they worship

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: The church recognises faith in God, belief in the omnipotence and omnipresence of the supreme being and requires members to trust him and give their devotion to him at all times

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that wisdom and understanding are derived from their supreme being and that to retain them in their purest form, individuals must acknowledge him at all times.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: The C & S church of Zion encourages members to stay well informed, exhibit discernment and display intelligence in their daily lives.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: The church places premium on the beauty of the spirit and the soul but also recognises how important people should maintain their natural beauty and groom themselves to keep their beauty. The church holds that attractiveness is good but other valuable virtues as those already identified are more beneficial to those who have them than striving to be attractive but neglecting those other virtues.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Physical cleanliness and orderliness are seen as great attributes among the C & S church of Zion. Members are encouraged to imbibe them

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The church teaches members never to take offence against God or think that he is capable of evil or doing wrong. This is one of the basic virtues members are taught to uphold

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No member of the church is mandated or stipulated to live a life of celibacy as a result of their faith.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The church teaches sexual fidelity with one's married partner. No other obligations or sexual restraints are placed on members. Unmarried members are however called to a life of sexual abstinence till they are married

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is not required of any member in the C & S church of Zion

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: There are occasions when members may be expected to fast as a form of self denial in carrying out a spiritual assignment

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: This may only be a sacrifice to obtain a more valuable substance from the supreme being.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: This is never practised in the C & S church of Zion

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: This is never practised in the C & S church of Zion

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No sacrifice of adults or minors is required in the church or among its members

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No sacrifice of children or minors is required in the church or among its members

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Suicide is not practiced by members of the church as a religious duty.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Sacrifice of property or valuable items is not required among the membership of the C & S church of Zion

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: At the headquarters of the C & S church of Zion, Ugbonla, members meet for religious programmes twice daily. The meetings are usually fairly short. They usually commence around 5:00 am and 5:00 pm and last just about an hour. On Sundays, they meet in the morning from about 10:00 am. The normal Sunday service last about three hours. However on special events, Sunday services could last longer than the usual hours.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Physical risk taking which counts for piety is not practised by members of the C & S church of Zion.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Ethical precepts such as truthfulness, honesty, love and others are preached and subscribed to by the C & S church of Zion

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Members outside the C & S church of Zion suffer serious no marginalisation from the group. The group desires that others join them in their worship and way of life but do not marginalise or discriminate against non members

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: No specified rituals are expected of members of the church except that they attend the church programmes and participate in group activities as members in good standing.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 200

Notes: I answered 200 above because the space will not allow explanations. In actual fact, all

members are expected in the large scale rituals. Attendance depends on the membership strength of each branch of the church. In Ugbonla, the headquarters of the church, people gather in their thousands at festivals, anniversaries and conventions.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 10

Notes: Ten hours is selected because two services hold daily in Ugbonla and the branches during special programmes. While the morning service starts at 5@00 am, the evening service commences no later than 5:00 pm as well.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: Proceedings of rituals are simple and can be followed in sequence by congregants, There is no need of orthodoxy checks in the performances of rituals in special programmes in the C & S church of Zion.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: Proceedings of rituals are simple and can be followed in sequence by congregants, There is no need of orthopraxy checks in the performances of rituals in special programmes in the C & S church of Zion.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Notes: Participation in religious activities in the C & S church of Zion does not entail synchronic practices.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: The use of intoxicants does not form part of the religious practices or observances of the C & S church of Zion.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Notes: Tattoos do not form a part of the extra-ritual in-group rituals among the membership of the C & S church of Zion.

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Only male infants are circumcised in the group. This is not necessarily an in-group requirement but a traditional practice among the larger Yoruba ethnic group which the Ilaje people belong to. The C & S church of Zion is dominated by the Ilaje people of the Yoruba stock.

↳ Food taboos:

– No

Notes: No strict food taboos exist among the church membership

↳ Hair:

– No

Notes: There is generally no extra-ritual in-group hair rituals among the people. The general convention is that men do not wear very long hair while women who wish can keep their hair and make acceptable hair styles of it.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Dresses constitute one of the most colourful extra-ritual in-group practices among the C & S church of Zion. Each group within the assembly apart from complying with the general ritual garment requirement of the church has developed in-group embellishment to the general prayer garment requirement of membership. This makes for in-group distinctiveness and adds colour and style to their ceremonies.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Though generally the use of ornaments is not compulsory among group members in the C & S church of Zion, they add flavour to, increase the distinctiveness of each group and makes each of them stand out from the others. If the idea of ornaments is stretched a bit further, certain components of the dresses or religious garments of members could be categorised under this umbrella. Apart from the religious dresses worn by members, certain embellishments hanged and in some cases sewn or worn over the usual dresses in prescribed colours and following a pattern could be placed in this category. Religious belts (girdles), caps of distinct shapes, heights and with particular inscriptions and other items make each group stand out and confers some uniqueness on them.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, special ritual languages are used by different groups. For example, the church choir and those with endearing voices who populate the music department supplying soul lifting melodious tunes during programmes are called Alore. No one takes the honour upon him/herself but it is conferred. Glossolalia is also a common practice used among the people.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: There are other distinct extra-ritual in-group practices found within sections or segments of the church membership. For example, prophets in the church have some distinct practices which manifest when conducting their ritual performances. They move around the meeting venue in some brisk manner, identifying a spiritual task and deploy a spiritual solution to them as inspired. The Cherubim group also have their modus operandi in conducting their affairs. This is true with other groups as they carry out their duties and functions in the church,

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The use of fictive kinship terminologies is an innovative idea brought into the Yoruba filial/kinship lexicon by theocratic communities introduced into the Ilaje area by the Yoruba speaking people who populate this segment of Yorubaland

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: The fictive kinship terminologies used in the C & S church of Zion is universal to the entire group.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The use of these terminologies is widespread. Members of the community are proud to identify themselves with the terms within and outside Ugbonla settlement.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: The fictive kinship terminology employed among the C & S church of Zion is common and widespread. They refer to themselves as "Omo Ilu Igbagbo or Omo Ugbonla" meaning those (members or children) of the community of faith or children of Ugbonla community.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The people refer to their village as a religious community. They operate a theocratic system of government. The community's leading prophet is the head of the church as well as the leader of the community. The founder of the community led the administration of the settlement from 1948 when it was founded to 1996 when he passed away. His son, is the second and current Oba of the community.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The church takes the welfare of her members serious. It gives support and aid to any member who requires assistance with basic needs including food, shelter, healthcare etc. Community members also run thrift and cooperative societies which has proven helpful to members who need business capital to support their private business outfits.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community runs the famine relief and aids it gives to members. A committee is constituted within the community to handle this task.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The relief given to members is provided to them as the need arises. The process of administering the relief has not been institutionalised.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Everything relating to the relief and its administration is fully handled by the community.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The community does not have an institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm. It is the duty of each family to meet the needs of the elderly and infirm. The community only comes in when the family is unable to meet this need satisfactorily.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community handles the process of providing substance to meet the needs of the elderly and infirm when it is established that the family is incapable of satisfactorily providing for their vulnerable members.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The church established a primary school in Ugbonla community which was instrumental to the education of their children and the literacy of their adult population. A secondary school was also established to help further the actualise the educational needs of her members. The community also went ahead to establish schools in other towns and villages where their branches are located.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Access to formal education is open to all members of the church.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Every member of the church has access to educational facilities provided by the community.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: The religious group has never outsourced the running, administration and control of its educational institutions to any individual or group

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The church has committees which coordinate most of their activities and programmes. They ensure standards are set and obligations are fulfilled so as to keep things in proper running order

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: When the need arises, group members interact with other bureaucracies in order to have their legitimate desires met. These may include government agencies, regulatory authorities among others

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The community does not provide a permanent public food storage. However, when the need arises to make food donations specifically for a given purpose or towards achieving a group objective, such food storages are set up to meet the needs. Such food storages would be closed once the purposes for which they were opened are concluded.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: It is only when the need arises that the religious group opens food storages. No institution carries out this responsibility on behalf of the religious group when the opening of food storages become necessary.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Because the community is located in a perennially wet region a few miles from the coast of the Atlantic Ocean, they experience heavy rains which result in flooding and for which much effort must be made to control flooding. They dredged canals and channelled run off water into streams and rivers around them

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The religious group handles its water management processes internally.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: The community had large passenger boat which moved people, goods and other items across the communities around the coast from Lagos in the east to Cameroon in the west.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The transportation infrastructure is not provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The religious group neither levies taxes nor tithes on members. It only seeks freewill offerings from members as they wished to give.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution is involved in the little collections the community takes from their members

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The institution established by the C & S church of Zion which polices the community is the Cherubim Band. It is a highly disciplined law enforcement band. Its operational base is in Ugbonla but its jurisdiction stretches to every locality where branches of the church are found. The band effectively provides security coverage as well as upholding the strict compliance to community conventions. Its officers are promoted according to their effectiveness. They are divided into units and departments with each department specialising in one aspect of their mandate. The leader of the band is responsible to the Oba of Ugbonla

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: For several decades after the founding of Ugbonla, the Police department in the country was quite satisfied with the operations of the Cherubim Band and was therefore pleased to give them the liberty to administer the internal affairs of the community. The Police Force did not interfere in anyway whatsoever regarding the policing of Ugbonla until very recently when the community itself provided a Police Post in the community though the Police Force is still being expected to send in officers to keep the place running.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Until 1996 when the founder of the community died, there was a group of elderly and experienced men who heard appeals from cases handled by the Cherubim Band. They sat as judges over appeals and were trusted to dispense justice appropriately. Only on rear cases were appeals further taken up for the final adjudication of the Oba. When the Oba (founder and king) of the community made a pronouncement over a matter, his decision stands. No further appeals could be made on a subject the Oba has ruled over.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Matters and disagreements between community members are handled exclusively through the mechanism provided by the church. Only on rare cases when either the community or leadership of the community is drawn in a matter with an outsider or an institution outside the community is such cases taken to an independent institution like the courts.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: The community enforces institutional punishment in accordance with its laws and conventions.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: The community has never handed capital punishment to any adherent or member since it was established.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in extreme cases and rare cases, folks found to have grossly contravened the established norms and laws of the community are excommunicated.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Notes: folks found to have committed certain serious infractions in community are given corporal punishment which include weeding community areas, clearing out blocked drainages, sand filling portions of the waterlogged community land among other things.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: While the community is investigating some categories of cases, it withholds the rights of those being investigated to certain privileges pending the outcome of the investigation.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Punishment for offenses in Ugbonla do not include the seizure of private property of indicted fellows.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Until recently when it appears that the internal control system of the community has degenerated, internal measures alone were used in punishing offenders in Ugbonla community.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The community has a form of legal code which not fully developed.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents are subject to the Nigerian legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: No institutional military force is in place in the community

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are free to join the Nigerian Armed Forces if they desire and are successful in the recruitment process.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are protected by and subject to the Nigerian Armed Forces.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The religious group has no distinct written language exclusively developed for its private use. The religious group uses the Yoruba language which is the local language used in their area.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba language had been in use in the Ilaje area and is still in use in Ugbonla and all towns and villages around the community till date

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The use of the Yoruba language has been in operation in the area for centuries. No specific institution is in charge of the enforcement of the use of the language. The customs and traditions of the people supports their use of this local language in their locality

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group uses the Gregorian calendar

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The religious group has no formal calendar. It uses the Gregorian calendar

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Though members of the religious group engage in farming and fishing activities, they do not produce enough to feed their community members. They rely on markets within and outside the community to meet their consumption needs.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No formal arrangement exists with any institution to meet the food supply needs of the adherents or the community.